

Manuscript on History and Humanities

Journal homepage:
<https://manuscriptology.org/index.php/MHH>

FIRST WAR OF INDEPENDENCE OF 1857: VIEW OF EARLY HISTORIANS

Mithalesh Kumar Singh (Research Scholar)

University Department of History, Tilkamanjhi Bhagalpur University
Bhagalpur

ABSTRACT

The revolt of 1857 was a decisive event in Indian history, but it has been interpreted differently by different historians according to their views. Early British historians like Sir John Lawrence, T.R. Holmes and Sir John Seely belittled it as a "soldier revolt" or "sepoymutiny" and considered it an unorganized and unsuccessful movement. According to them, it was a sudden incident of military discontent, in which there was no national sentiment. Some other British historians called it "religious hypocrisy" or "Hindu-Muslim conspiracy" and considered it a mere coincidence against British rule.

On the other hand, early Indian nationalist historians like R.C. Majumdar, K.M. Panikkar and Savitribai Phule etc. considered it a widespread resistance of the people against British exploitation and unjust policies. They called it "India's first freedom struggle" and considered it an early expression of national consciousness. V.D. Savarkar described it as a well-planned, organised and widespread revolution in his famous book *The Struggle for Independence of 1857*. According to him, it involved not only soldiers, but also farmers, landlords, craftsmen, saints and the general public. Marxist historians such as Karl Marx also called it a "revolt of the masses" in contemporary writings and presented it as a struggle against the exploitation of British imperialism. He considered it a mass outrage resulting from socio-economic inequalities and colonialism. Subaltern historians did not consider 1857 as only a soldier's revolt or a struggle of leaders, but emphasized the active role of the common people in it. According to them, this movement was also a resistance of farmers, tribals, labourers, artisans and lower classes. They showed that at the local level, the rebellion was also against social, economic and

ARTICLE HISTORY

Submitted/Received: 10 Jun 2025

First Revised: 15 Jun 2025

Accepted: 17 Jul 2025

Publication Date: 22 Aug 2025

KEYWORDS:

Historians, Revolt, Farmers, Movement, Landlords, Freedom, Journalists, Tradition, Intelligentsia, Contemporary, Nationalist, Communist, Rebellion, National movement.

cultural inequalities. Thus, they considered 1857 a symbol of collective consciousness and resistance of the exploited classes. Thus, while early British historians described 1857 as merely a "military revolt" and "local disturbance", the Indian nationalist and Marxist viewpoint considered it the first phase of the freedom struggle. In conclusion, this revolt was the beginning of national consciousness in Indian history, which later laid a strong foundation for the freedom movement.

© 2025 <https://manuscriptology.org>

Full Article

Historiography is always based on available sources. But it is also true that history is often written by the victors, not by the defeated. For this reason, war is fought not only on the battlefield but also on the pages of history. The victorious class suppresses the memory of the defeated and imposes its ideology, due to which the defeated groups are deprived of their real history.¹ The same thing happened after the revolt of 1857. The British not only crushed the revolt, but also completely banned any voice of dissent or resistance. As a result, most of the available sources were written by British officers, diplomats, soldiers, journalists and historians, which were preserved in the form of letters, diaries, government records and reports. Based on these sources, history was written from an imperialist perspective and the nature of 1857 was narrowed down.

Evidence about the behaviour of the British is available only by looking at one-sided sources created by the colonial rulers. Some army officers happily wrote to their families about how they killed rebels in revenge, hanged them and tied them to cannons and blew them up. There is also evidence of the trials and court proceedings of the time of these events, where material related to the charges and information can be obtained. Letters and reports written by native spies during the occupation of Delhi also provide invaluable information about the struggles of the rebels and how these spies were passing on their information to the British. There are also photographs and sketches in which scenes of wars and rebels hanging from gallows made in trees or huts can be seen.² Vinayak Damodar Savarkar is credited with starting this tradition of turning the sources around, which was later popularised by Ranjit Guha as 'new knowledge' of turning the facts around. Thus, there are many streams of historiography of the revolt of 1857, inspired by different ideologies.

First of all, it is important to mention the imperialist historiography here. For about 50 years after the rebellion, this ideology had a great influence on the writing of the history of the rebellion. The image of the rebels created by this type of writing is that they were uncivilized, uncultured, robbers, blind criminals and goons, who rebelled against a government that was civilized, cultured and a peaceful protector of the justice system. Therefore, the behavior of the rebels against the British people was shameful, condemnable because all their actions were illegal and against the law. What the British did against the rebels could be justified because they were dealing with criminals and traitors. Therefore, their hanging, murder, imprisonment, blowing up with cannon, confiscation of property were all legal. The punishments were legal and their purpose was to prevent any rebellion in the future. Many English historians like K. Malleon, John Lawrence, Seeley, Trevelyan, Secretary of India Stanley, Holmes, Marshman, etc., who were natural supporters of the empire, have presented it in this form.³

According to Sir John Lawrence and Seeley, it was only a 'military revolt' and nothing else. Agreeing with them, Secretary of India Stanley, K. Malleon, Trevelyan, Dadwell and Roberts etc. also called it a military revolt. Mr. L.E.R. Rees called it a 'struggle of religious fanatics against Christians'. British historians like T.R. Holmes have tried to popularize the idea that it was a 'war between barbarism and civilization'. Whereas Sir James Outram and W. Taylor called this revolt the result of a 'Hindu-Muslim conspiracy', whose aim was to re-establish Muslim rule.⁴ Overall, all British writers establish their view that it was a rebellion against their legal and legitimate government. Among them also, most historians have called it a 'Sepoy Revolt' which was limited only to the army and which did not receive the support of the general public. Apart from British historians, contemporary British newspapers also represent basically imperialist thinking. According to the 'London Times', our aim should be to maintain our continuous control over India by any means. Although this newspaper opposed the massacre committed by the Indians, it also properly noted the taking hold of the seeds of nationalism.⁵ In this context, the views of Disraeli, the leader of the opposition in Britain, are also very important. At the same time, in the House of Commons, he called it not a 'Sepoy Mutiny' but a 'National Mutiny'.⁶

On the other hand, due to the terror of oppression and atrocities for a period of 50 years after the revolt, no Indian was able to muster the courage to write about the revolt of 1857 from his own perspective and there was a terrible silence among the Indian intelligentsia. Maulana Abul Kalam Azad has also underlined this in

Surendra Nath Sen's book *Eighteen Hundred Fifty-Seven*.⁷ Hence, in the opinion of some contemporary Indians also, it was a military revolt. Munshi Jeevanlal and Muinuddin (who were in Delhi at that time), Durgadas Bandhopadhyay (who was in Bareilly at that time), Sir Syed Ahmed Khan (who was on the post of Sadar Amin in Bijnor in 1857) and Mirla Ghalib expressed similar views. The silence of Indians regarding this revolt was broken when Vinayak Damodar Savarkar made the revolt of 1857 a part of Indian nationalist history writing. His book *Bharat Ka Swatantrata Samar* was published in 1909. The year 1907 was a special year in the context of the revolt because the 50th anniversary of the revolt was completed this year. The concept of this presentation was completely different from imperialist history writing and the events were analyzed from the Indian point of view. The British government banned this book but it reached the people and became very popular. This book was a source of inspiration for revolutionaries like Bhagat Singh and Hardayal.

Between 1945 and 1952, Pandit Nehru, Manmath Nath Gupta and Maulana Azad through their writings explained the causes, nature and consequences of this revolt on a wide scale from an Indian perspective. They also set a standard for writing the history of revolt. Jawaharlal Nehru has written about the revolt of 1857- "This revolt was inevitable, which was the result of their anger against exploitation. The farmers were ruined by famine and were being crushed by new economic burdens. The newly educated people were looking towards the West and were hoping that India would progress due to their generosity. The same thing was more or less in Southern and Western India, Madras and Bombay. But there was no such inclination in the northern towns and the feeling of revolt was growing among the common people, especially among the feudal chieftains and their followers. Anti-British sentiment was also spread among the people."⁸

According to Maulana Azad, a prominent Indian leader and thinker, the nature and area of this great struggle has long been controversial, both in India and abroad. All the books written on this struggle represent the same view that it was a rebellion of the Indian army against the constitutional government of the time. It has been accepted in them that Indian princely states also took part in this rebellion, but they were princely states which were taken over by Lord Dalhousie. That is why there was anger among them. The British government, as the ruler of the country, crushed this rebellion and established peace.⁹ In the context of writing the history of this rebellion, he believed that the time has come to write a new and unbiased history of the movement of 1857 because being a hundred years old event, its intensity has almost ended now. Along with this, the relevance of the political objectives fulfilled by it has also ended. Therefore, now such an environment exists in which it is possible to study the events of 1857 in an objective and neutral manner and a 'neither condemnation nor praise' approach can be adopted towards the conflict. In the same sequence, he has underlined the 'Indian silence' in the atmosphere of fear and terror created after the ruthless suppression of the revolt and considered the lack of an Indian perspective in the writing of the history of 1857 as natural. Even on the occasion of the centenary of the revolt, Maulana Azad was the inspiration behind the writing of the official history of 1857 written by S.N. Sen.

Many authors wrote books and articles on the 100th anniversary of this revolt. Prominent among these authors were R.C. Majumdar, S.N. Sen, P.C. Joshi, Ramvilas Sharma, S.B. Chaudhary, Ashok Mehta, K.K. Dutta etc. It would be necessary to underline the point in the context of their writings that for the first time a serious and in-depth study of the revolt of 1857 began and an attempt was made to understand it from an Indian perspective. Another aspect of their writings is that these authors had differences in their concepts and principles related to the cause, nature and consequences of this revolt. But for the first time they used various sources on a wide scale. With this, a period of writing a solid alternative history as opposed to imperialist history writing begins. Historian R.C. Majumdar refuses to consider it as India's 'First War of Independence'. He believes that except for some minor incidents, there is nothing in that rebellion that suggests that the views of the soldiers and the main heroes of this rebellion were influenced by nationalism anywhere. According to him, it was born out of the resentment of certain disgruntled groups against the British and choosing it in the framework of nationalism would be a simplistic explanation of the rebellion.¹⁰

On the other hand, according to historian Surendra Nath Sen, this rebellion was inevitable because no slave

country can accept foreign rule for long. This kind of resistance was not different from the conflict between the Indians and the British. Indian soldiers were just an important link between the colonial rule and the Indian people. Somewhere their dissatisfaction and protest was highlighting the anger of the Indian people.¹¹ Here it is also appropriate to underline the opinion of S.B. Chaudhary. According to him, if seen in its larger perspective, it can be said that in the history of India, such a large-scale rebellion of different groups was not seen as widespread as that of 1857. According to S.B. Chaudhary's book *Theories of Indian Revolt 1857-59*, this battle against foreign power, which lasted for more than a year, was in itself a supernatural chapter of Indian history. Ashok Mehta, in his book *The Great Revolt*, tried to prove that the nature of the rebellion of 1857 was national.¹²

Communist leader P.C. Joshi has written a long article in his edited book *Rebellion 1857: A Symposium* in the context of 1857. In this, he has tried to understand the ideological and theoretical questions and its expansion, leadership and failures in a serious manner. He has started his article with the fact that till now the Indian side of the rebellion had not been fully exposed and it is possible that this incident is still stuck in the quagmire of controversies whether it was a mere 'Sepoy Mutiny' or 'a national rebellion'.¹³ Writer Ramvilas Sharma, in his book '*Saan Sattavan Ki Rajya Kranti*', explained the reasons, nature and consequences of the rebellion in a broad perspective and equated it with the Russian Revolution and the French Revolution and accepted it as a national freedom struggle.

Eric Strokes' book *The Peasant Armed: Indian rebellion of 1857* is an important intervention in the discussion of this mass rebellion. Strokes gave a new direction to this discussion. According to him, the nature of this rebellion should be seen in the perspective of the 'rural and urban continuity' of Indian society. The 'sepoy' of the East India Company came from the rural areas of India and his medals and uniform could separate him from his environment to some extent, but basically he was not cut off from his caste, religious, social and economic rural perspective. The process of colonial exploitation which was present uniformly throughout India was affecting his family and his environment somewhere.¹⁴

As a result of the publication of the book *Elementary Aspects of Peasant Insurgency in Colonial India* by Ranjit Guha, a leading writer of the stream of Sullyturn history writing, emphasis was laid on examining and understanding the viewpoint and strategy of the common man from his own perspective rather than from the viewpoint of the elite. Hence, Ranjit Guha has written in the context of this rebellion that the voice of the rebels can be identified from the documents of the British themselves, such as reports, mandates, letters, legal decisions etc. This method is useful for a detailed analysis of the revolt because it is an unfortunate fact that to understand the Indian side of the revolt, we have to see and understand the documents preserved by the British.¹⁵

Continuing this sequence, historians like Varun Dey, Irfan Habib, Amar Farooqui, Rudranshu Mukherjee, Tapti Rai, Rajatkant Ray, Savyasachi Bhattacharya, Amresh Mishra, Vismoypati etc. have given a new perspective to the various aspects of this revolt such as its vastness, its various dimensions, its strength, background, form, extent and sources in their works. Not only this, on the 150th anniversary of this revolt, a lot of work has been done on the facts, evidences, documents, folk songs and folk heroes related to this revolt in almost the whole of India and various books, magazines, special issues (*Udbhavan*, *Media*, *Vasudha*) etc. have been published. In this way, this revolt of 1857 is being taken out of the so-called image of 'Sepoy Revolt' and is being seen as a civil and national revolt.

Conclusion:-

The First War of Independence of 1857 was a turning point in Indian history, which was interpreted by various early historians from their own perspectives. British historians generally belittled it by calling it a "soldier revolt" or "local discontent" and refused to give it the form of a national movement. They believed that it was merely the discontent of a few soldiers, which lacked organization and a broader purpose. On the other hand, Indian nationalist historians considered it the first strong spark that arose against British imperialist exploitation and repression. They called it "India's First War of Independence" and highlighted it

as the beginning of the national movement. Thinkers like V.D. Savarkar described this rebellion as a well-planned and widespread revolution, in which there was active cooperation of soldiers as well as farmers, landlords, artisans and the public. On the other hand, the Marxist view considered it as a class struggle and the public's reaction against colonialism. Karl Marx, in his writings, described it as an expression of socio-economic resentment arising from colonial exploitation. On the contrary, subaltern historians tried to understand it from the bottom up and put the role of the common people, workers and rural society at its center. It is clear from these different interpretations that the struggle of 1857 was not just a military discontent, but all social, religious, economic and political elements were active in it. This rebellion could not succeed in the current circumstances, but it gave birth to the feeling of independence in the minds of the Indian people and prepared the background for the coming national movements.

So in conclusion it can be said that the first freedom struggle of 1857 was the first comprehensive effort to lay the foundation of national consciousness in Indian history, which can be understood from different perspectives, but its reality is that it opened the first door to the path of freedom. At present, the 168th anniversary of this struggle of 1857 has been celebrated. Research work is being done continuously and new aspects are being revealed. This discussion, which started with the Sepoy Rebellion, has reached various forms like the First Indian War of Independence, National Rebellion, Civil Rebellion, People's Rebellion, State Revolution, People's Revolution etc. This means that even today there are differences in its interpretations. These differences at the ideological level are enriching its study further.

Reference List and Footnotes: -

1. S. B. Chaudhuri Civil Rebellion in the Indian Mutinies, 1857–1859 Calcutta: World Press, 1957.
2. Mubarak Ali, 1857: Itihas ka punarnirman, Kamala Prasad (ed.) Pragatisheel Vasudha, Issue-76, Bhopal, January-March 2008, p. 107.
3. Ibid, p. 108.
4. Snigdha Sen, The Historiography of the Indian Revolt of 1857, Calcutta: Punthi-Pustak, 1992
5. B. L. Grover, Yashpal, Aadhunika Bharat ka itihas, New Delhi, 2002, p. 183.
6. Pradeep Saxena (ed.), Hamare itihas me 1857, New Delhi, 2012, p. 65.
7. Maulana Abul Kalam Azad, 1857 ki prastavna, by Surendranath Sen, New Delhi, 2005, pp. xi-xxvii.
8. Jawaharlal Nehru, Hindustan ki kahani, New Delhi 2018, p. 373.
9. Ibid, Maulana Abul Kalam Azad, pp. xi-xii.
10. R.C. Majumdar, The Sepoy Mutiny and the Revolt of 1857, Calcutta, 1963, p. 104.
11. J.W. Kaye, Bharat me sipahi widroh ka itihas, 1857-58, London, 1864, pp. 13-19.
12. S.B. Chaudhuri, Bhartiya widroh ke sidhant, 1857-1859, Calcutta, 1965.
13. P.C. Joshi, The Revolt of 1857: A Symposium, Delhi, 1957, pp. 57-58.
14. Eric Stokes, The Peasant and the Raj, Cambridge, 1978, pp.
15. Pradeep Saxena (ed.), 1857, Nirantarta aur pariwartan, New Delhi, 2007, A pp.204-06.